

IMPROVING THE INVESTMENT CLIMATE IN AGRICULTURE AND THE ROLE OF DIGITAL PLATFORMS IN THE FRUIT AND VEGETABLE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes the legal, economic and infrastructural foundations of attracting investments to the agricultural sector in Uzbekistan. The content of the reforms being implemented in such areas as improving the investment climate, guaranteeing the rights of investors, creating tax and financial incentives, and improving infrastructure is highlighted. As part of the study, a monographic survey was conducted among farms and agricultural firms engaged in fruit and vegetable growing, identifying investment practices in the sector, existing barriers and needs. Practical proposals were also put forward to ensure information transparency by creating a digital platform, digitize investment processes, and increase efficiency in the sector

Introduction. In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing consistent reforms to improve investment policy and attract investments to all sectors of the national economy, in particular to the agricultural sector. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasized, "investment is the driver of the economy," and its volume and efficiency are the main guarantees of the country's sustainable development.

A number of regulatory legal acts adopted in our country have created a legal and institutional basis for systematic work in this direction. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026", as well as the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 16 dated January 14, 2023 "On measures to further improve the system for forming the Investment Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan and increase its effectiveness" are aimed at improving investment processes in the country, creating a favorable environment for foreign and domestic investors, and increasing the activity of the private sector.

The agricultural sector is of strategic importance in the national economy, and its sustainable development is closely related to the volume, composition and efficiency of investments. In particular, the fruit and vegetable sector is one of the areas with great export potential, but is not fully developed due to infrastructural and financial barriers. Therefore, the issues of improving the mechanism for attracting investments in this sector, creating modern infrastructure and introducing digital management are of urgent importance. Today,

the Single Window system, public-private partnership (PPP) projects, tax and financial incentives, as well as reforms aimed at introducing a digital economy in the country are improving the investment climate. At the same time, the implementation of information platforms such as the AgroInvest Hub plays an important role in increasing the transparency and efficiency of investment processes in agriculture. From this point of view, this study aims to analyze the investment environment in the fruit and vegetable sector using the example of the Tashkent region, identify existing problems, and develop proposals to increase the efficiency of the sector through digitalization of investment processes.

To attract and effectively direct investments in the country, it is necessary to improve the legal, economic, infrastructural and human capital conditions. Reforms in this area are closely interconnected and are reflected in the following areas. To strengthen the investment climate, first of all, the rights of investors must be legally guaranteed. Adopting laws on investment protection, forming an independent and effective judicial system, as well as reducing bureaucratic barriers, will create a favorable and reliable environment for investors. Also, guaranteeing land and property rights will increase investors' confidence in long-term investment decisions. Along with legal guarantees, financial and tax incentives also play an important role in attracting investors. Financial assistance for business is provided through reduced tax rates, the creation of free economic zones, credit guarantees, subsidies and grants. This, in turn, serves as an important opportunity and motivation, especially for new investors. It is important that the infrastructure necessary for investors' activities is well developed - electricity, gas, transport and logistics networks. The construction of technoparks and industrial zones, the improvement of digital infrastructure will significantly facilitate business operations and increase the efficiency of investment returns. The state's active dialogue policy is of great importance in attracting investors. The introduction of the "Single Window" system will centralize services. Direct contacts are established through investor forums, exhibitions, and international conferences. Partnership projects between the public and private sectors also create great opportunities. Promoting the country or individual sectors on the international stage is also an important component of the investment climate. The country is presented as attractive for investment by improving its position in international ratings, publishing advertisements and articles in foreign media, and preparing promotional videos and booklets. High-quality human capital is one of the main factors for any investment project. Human resource potential is increased by establishing specialized vocational training centers, attracting foreign specialists, and providing investors with accurate information about local personnel.

As part of the study, a monographic survey was conducted among 125 farms, agrofirms and business entities engaged in fruit and vegetable growing in the Tashkent region. This survey provided an opportunity to in-depth study of the investment environment in the sector, attraction practices, existing problems and prospects. Based on the data obtained, practical analyses were conducted in the following areas:

60% of the farms surveyed (75 farms) reported that they had attracted investments from various sources in the past five years. These investments were mainly made at the expense of subsidies and preferential loans allocated within the framework of state programs.

In particular, we can see that 40 farms used state subsidies, 16 farms attracted loans from commercial banks, and 19 farms operated in partnership with private local investors.

At the same time, there were no cases involving the participation of foreign investors. This indicates that, although there is an investment environment in the region, relations with the external market are not sufficiently developed. Factors such as the lack of information transparency and guarantee mechanisms for private investors, and the insufficient formation of an environment of trust are the main obstacles in this regard.

The investments attracted are structurally mainly aimed at strengthening the production base. The analysis shows that investment funds were spent in the following areas:

Figure 1. Areas where investment funds were spent by farmers, peasants, and homesteads (n=125) ¹

This situation indicates that the production processes are being gradually modernized. However, there is almost no investment in processing and export infrastructure. This leads to the sale of raw materials instead of processing, increased dependence on the domestic market, and, as a result, the low cost of products. The analysis showed that 68% of the farms surveyed do not have warehouses for storing products. 76% do not have small-capacity workshops, equipment and technologies necessary for processing products. At the same time, 52% of farms noted problems with logistics. For example, poor road conditions, a lack of special refrigerated transport, and excessive intermediaries in accessing the market are among the main factors contributing to the decline in farmers' incomes. This indicates the need to expand opportunities for attracting investment in infrastructure. If the storage, processing and logistics system is not improved, the growth in production will not fully yield its results.

The majority of entities participating in the survey identified the following as the main problems in attracting investment:

¹ Compiled by the author based on survey data

Figure 2. The main problems in investment attraction highlighted by farmers, peasants, households (n=125)²

This situation means that access to investment is limited, especially for small farmers and family farms. Most of them do not have sufficient capacity to write, present, calculate investment projects and negotiate with investors. According to the survey results, participants expressed a high need for the following areas:

Figure 3. According to the results of the survey, the areas where the needs of the participants are high (n=125)³

This shows that farmers and other agricultural entities face more problems at the post-production stages (processing, sales, export). Therefore, investment should cover not only land and seeds, but all links of the value chain.

The results of the monographic survey show that there is an investment environment in the fruit and vegetable sector in the Tashkent region, but in practice there are many obstacles that limit the full use of this environment. The following measures are proposed to attract private and foreign investors:

Organize advisory centers for the development and presentation of investment projects for small farmers;

² Compiled by the author based on survey data

³ Compiled by the author based on survey data

Prepare projects for processing and storage infrastructure on the basis of public-private partnerships (PPPs);

Create an “agro-investment portal” with special legal, financial and technical information for investors;

Develop logistics centers for export-oriented products, etc.

In this regard, in our opinion, the implementation of the “AgroInvest Hub” platform and its further improvement in the future are of urgent importance. Today, it is necessary to develop methodological approaches that substantiate the essence and significance of the goals and objectives of a specific strategy chosen, and through them to make additions and changes that will serve as the basis for improving the e-agricultural strategy.

The “AgroInvest Hub” digital platform is of great importance in attracting investments and developing the industry in the fruit and vegetable sector. Because, first of all, accurate, accurate and fast information is necessary for making any investment and economic decision. Effective organization of the information flow in the agricultural sector through the implementation of the platform will bring great benefits to both producers and consumers.

Transparency and accurate information in investment processes: real data on production volumes, reserve status, and export-import opportunities will significantly reduce the likelihood of making wrong decisions. This will ensure stability in domestic and foreign markets.

Production and market balance: without accurate information about the volume of production, farmers and peasants may face over- or underproduction, which will lead to a sharp increase or decrease in prices. AgroInvest Hub allows you to predict these processes in advance.

Logistics and supply chain efficiency: the ability to accurately forecast the total production volume helps to effectively organize the logistics system (storage, cold storage, transportation). This reduces product losses and expands export opportunities.

A reliable environment for investors: a transparent database and a digital monitoring system allow investors to see the real status of projects and make the right decisions.

In our opinion, the implementation and use of the AgroInvest Hub digital platform in production creates the following opportunities:

1. Accurate data for farmers and peasant farms - the opportunity to obtain reliable information about which types of fruits and vegetables are advisable to grow will be created. For this, it is important that the data uploaded to the platform is accurate and accurate. Therefore, it is planned to constantly involve industry specialists and experts to analyze the information of the AgroInvest Hub.

2. Promoting a smart agricultural system - attention will be paid to monitoring all producers through a single electronic system. The platform will establish procedures for uploading and using data, as well as a clear distribution of responsibility for the authenticity of the uploaded data, ensuring mutual harmony in the system.

3. Expanding information sources - the platform will not be limited only to data uploaded by subscribers, but will also be provided with information from unmanned aerial vehicles (drones, sensors, etc.). This will allow achieving high accuracy in analyzing the uploaded data.

4. Planning of agrotechnical measures and protective measures - by analyzing the uploaded information, it will be possible to determine various agrotechnical measures, including recommendations on measures to protect plants from pests. At the same time, the platform's activities are financed by the Ministry of Agriculture and established tariffs, ensuring its stable operation based on financial incentives allocated by the state.

It is also important to introduce a single electronic website and online platform within the framework of the AgroInvest Hub in order to attract investments in the fruit and vegetable sector and support the development of the sector. Through this website, the process of exchanging ideas, innovative proposals and information will be effectively organized through the relevant channels. Such an opportunity will create an opportunity for farmers and peasant farms to get acquainted with practical innovative innovations, find solutions to existing problems and obstacles, and be aware of market trends. It is also planned to establish coworking centers as a separate service area of the platform. They will form an open space for dialogue between practicing farmers, researchers and investors, and will serve for the rapid implementation of the proposed ideas.

In general, with the increasing attention to investment issues and the increase in scientific research and published literature on them, there are various opinions and scientific and methodological approaches to the concept of "investment attractiveness". Based on their analysis, we can make a general conclusion that investment attractiveness is an important factor ensuring the sustainable and effective development of the economic system at the sectoral level.

Agriculture in Uzbekistan is one of the important sectors of the national economy, and improving the investment climate is of great importance for its sustainable development. In recent years, a number of decisions and programs adopted by the state, aimed at modernizing agriculture, expanding private sector participation, and introducing innovative technologies, have accelerated reforms in the sector.

In conclusion, attracting investment in agriculture ensures economic growth, creates new jobs, and strengthens the country's export potential. Therefore, increasing investment attractiveness should remain a priority task for the government, the private sector, and academic institutions in cooperation.

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